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Companies operating in the production of textile and clothing products in OECD countries

It decreased on average by 3.87% between 2005 and 2022

The OECD calculates the number of companies operating in the production of textile and clothing products. Data is available for the period 2005-2022.

Firms operating in the production of textile and clothing products in OECD countries in 2022. In 2022, the textile and clothing production sector showed a varied distribution of companies across European countries, highlighting significant differences in terms of industrial presence. By analyzing the data provided, we can observe the dynamics of the sector in various countries, from the prominent role of some nations to the more modest presence of others. Italy leads the sector with 38,070 companies, followed by France with 30,865 companies. This primacy for Italy is not surprising, considering the country's historic tradition in fashion and textiles, renowned for its high-quality craftsmanship, luxury brands and design innovations. France, also an epicenter of global fashion, maintains a strong position thanks to its famous fashion brands and ability to combine tradition and modernity in textile design. Czechia and Poland, with 18,136 and 17,957 companies respectively, emerge as important textile production hubs in Central Europe. The competitiveness of these countries comes from relatively low production costs and proximity to Western European markets. Romania, with 9,255 companies, continues to be a key player in the sector thanks to its skilled workforce and competitive costs. Spain and Portugal have 15,010 and 12,218 companies respectively, reflecting the importance of these countries in European textile production. Spain is known for its vibrant fashion sector and global brands such as Zara, while Portugal is renowned for the quality of its manufacturing and the production of high-quality fabrics, especially in linen and knitwear. Germany, with 6,872 companies, is not among the main producers, but maintains an important role in the European textile sector thanks to its capacity for technological innovation and the production of high-quality technical and industrial fabrics. This market segment differentiates Germany from other countries with a higher concentration of companies in the fashion and consumer apparel sector. The Netherlands (5,868 companies) and Slovakia (5,736 companies) demonstrate a significant presence in the textile sector, benefiting from a favorable business environment and their strategic position in Europe. Greece, with 5,021 companies, continues to maintain a strong textile tradition, although the sector has faced numerous economic challenges in recent years. Countries such as Finland (3,142 companies), Sweden (3,169 companies) and Serbia (2,690 companies) have a less pronounced presence in the textile sector. These countries, despite having fewer companies, can boast specific market niches, such as sustainable and innovative fabrics. At the bottom of the list we find countries such as Luxembourg (22 companies) and Malta (170 companies). These countries, due to their limited geographic and demographic size, have a marginal presence in the textile and clothing sector. The analysis of 2022 data shows a varied map of textile and clothing production in Europe and in some non-European countries. Countries with a long tradition in the sector, such as Italy and France, continue to dominate in terms of the number of companies. At the same time, Central and

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Eastern Europe is emerging as a new frontier in textile production thanks to competitive costs and increasing quality of labor.

Companies operating in the production of textile and clothing products in OECD countries between 2015 and 2022. The analysis of the textile and clothing production sector from 2005 to 2022 highlights significant changes in the various countries, with a marked variability in the dynamics growth and decline of active businesses. We explore the data for each country in detail, analyzing the possible causes and implications of these variations. Costa Rica emerges as the country with the highest percentage growth, recording an increase of 259.76%. The number of companies increased from 656 to 2,360, suggesting notable development in the sector. This could be attributed to favorable economic policies, government incentives to attract foreign investment and proximity to North American markets, making Costa Rica an attractive manufacturing hub. Slovak Republic experienced an extraordinary increase of 1,188.99%, going from 445 to 5,736 companies. This boom is likely linked to the country's integration into the European Union, which has facilitated access to European markets, as well as industrial support policies and investments in infrastructure. France saw a 90% increase, with the number of businesses rising from 16,245 to 30,865. France's growth can be explained by the country's continued relevance in the fashion and luxury sector, combined with strong support for innovation and sustainability in the textile sector. The Netherlands recorded an increase of 108.97%, with the number of companies increasing from 2,808 to 5,868. This increase may be due to the growth of e-commerce and the demand for innovative and sustainable textile products. Estonia and Lithuania increased the number of their textile enterprises by 73.06% and 65.12% respectively. These increases reflect the adoption of advanced technologies, integration into European Union markets and a focus on quality and innovation. Austria and Latvia also showed notable growth, with increases of 46.85% and 43.05% respectively. The increase in Austria could be attributed to a strong textile tradition and policies supporting SMEs, while in Latvia the growth can be linked to investments in modernization and green technologies. Italy, once the main player in the European textile sector, saw a drastic decrease of 37.42%, going from 60,831 to 38,070 companies. This significant decline could be due to various factors, including the relocation of production to lower-cost countries, the 2008 economic crisis, and increased global competition. Despite this, Italy continues to maintain a strong reputation for high-quality products and innovative design. Spain and Portugal recorded reductions of 31.87% and 27.21% respectively. Spain went from 22,031 to 15,010 companies, while Portugal from 16,786 to 12,218. These declines can be attributed to the economic and financial crisis that has hit both countries hard, along with increasing competition from low-cost producers. Slovenia, Hungary and Poland also saw significant declines in the number of textile businesses, with declines of 30.08%, 30.06% and 20.95% respectively. These countries may have been impacted by globalization and the offshoring of production, as well as a possible lack of investment in the sector. Denmark and Sweden recorded reductions of 24.56% and 20.14% respectively. These Nordic countries, despite having a strong tradition in textile design, may have suffered due to high production costs and global competition. Belgium, Bulgaria and Luxembourg saw smaller but still significant reductions in the number of businesses. Belgium went from 2,540 to 2,071 companies (-18.46%), Bulgaria from 5,434 to 4,226 (-22.23%) and Luxembourg from 41 to 22 (-46.34%). These changes may be due to a combination of economic factors, including changes in global demand and domestic economic challenges. Germany saw modest growth of 2.20%, with the number of businesses rising from 6,724 to 6,872. Germany's stability in the textile sector can be attributed to its specialization in technical and industrial textiles, sectors less vulnerable to competition from low-cost producers. Romania recorded a growth of 11.08%, with the number of companies increasing from 8,332 to 9,255. This increase, although modest, indicates stability in the Romanian textile sector, which benefits from competitive labor costs and growing integration into

European supply chains. Analysis of data covering the period 2005-2022 in the textile and apparel manufacturing sector reveals a varied landscape with some countries seeing significant increases in the number of businesses, while others have suffered substantial declines. The reasons behind these variations are multiple, including economic factors, government policies, investments in technology and innovation, and globalization. Countries such as Costa Rica and the Slovak Republic have benefited from favorable economic conditions and incentive policies that have stimulated the growth of the sector. In contrast, countries such as Italy and Spain have faced economic challenges and increasing global competition that have led to a reduction in the number of textile businesses. The future of the textile sector in Europe and other regions will depend on countries' ability to adapt to global changes, invest in innovation and sustainability, and maintain global competitiveness.

Conclusions. The number of companies operating in the textile and clothing sector decreased on average by 3.87% between 2005 and 2022 for the countries considered. In particular, the number of companies operating in the textile and clothing sector grew by 1188.99% in the Slovak Republic, by 259.76% in Costa Rica, and by 108.97% in the Netherlands. The value of companies operating in the textile and clothing sector decreased between 2005 and 2022 in the following countries: Spain with -31.87%, Italy with -37.42% and Luxembourg with -46.34%. Italy is the country that has suffered the greatest losses in the textile and clothing sector with -22,761 companies between 2005 and 2022. However, despite this significant loss of companies, Italy still leads the ranking of countries by number of companies in the textile and clothing sector in 2022. With the number of companies operating in the textile and clothing sector equal to 100 in 2022, 18.31% are located in Italy, 14.84% in France, 8.72 % in the Czech Republic, and 8.63% in Poland.

Number of Enterprises in the Textile and Clothing Sector (2022)

Declarations

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